

FAMILY HOLDING IS A PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISM OF SOCIALIZATION OF A CHILD

**Karimova V.M. Doctor of Psychological Sciences, professor,
Shamsiev U.B. Doctor of Psychological Sciences (DSc)
Umarova N.Sh. PhD in Psychological Sciences, Associate Professor
(Uzbekistan)**

Abstract: this article thoroughly clarified the conceptual idea of “primary communication and caring attitude.” This in its opinion and arguments grounded in literary analysis as well as scientific conclusions personal research.

Keywords: primary communication, caring attitude, physical, biological and psychological freedom during infancy and childhood.

It is known how important the mother-child-father relationship is in adapting a child to the social environment, family, family relations, in personal-parental relationships in order to find their place. But one and the other side of this issue is that the physical, psychological and spiritual health of the child is indirectly affected by the overload and the content of the family environment, family holding and mutual emotional relations in the holding "mother-child", which is at his disposal.

In this regard, it is worth noting that the state pays great attention to the education of young people, a healthy mother and a healthy child, up to the construction of a family. Such care provides a foundation for children from infancy to their arrival in a healthy world, both physiologically and biologically, and for their quick access to the social environment. It is well known that the main factor that serves the formation of a child as a person, his socialization, that is, his entry into a big life, his place among people, is the relationship between a person in the family and a person in the family, which has been studied in many studies. However, the relationship of parents, spouses, sisters, brothers in the family, as well as the role of mother, father, sister, brothers in the formation and socialization of the personality of a newborn child were poorly studied in a separate study. In this regard, we found it necessary to express some feedback about the importance of the mother's personality in the socialization of the child.

It is known that before the birth of a child and in the process of ontogenesis, there is a direct influence of the mother on its formation and development. During the birth of a child, personal relationships in the family are important, that is, parental relationships, the peculiarities of the psychological state of the mother, her attitude to pregnancy. The fact that the mental state of the mother during pregnancy affects the formation and development of the child has also been proven by numerous studies. However, it is known that the mental state of a woman also affects the sex of the fetus in different ways. It can also be noted that the mental state of the mother affects the boy more than the girl, and this is also significant in the period after the birth of the child. Also, one of the problems that are in the focus of researchers' attention is the question of strengthening the mother-child-adult relationship, as well as the influence of maternal sincerity, cordial attitude on the child in the embryonic and postnatal development of the child. In this regard, the psychological state of the mother, which is in the focus of science of the XXI century, can be explained by the transition of the Uzbek folk phrase "Mother is a hero (ALP – ONADAN)" on the question of its impact on the child's vital activity. This also confirms our view above that even in the qualities of youth there will be a direct influence of the mother. After all, in this proverb, which has been formed for centuries and is being formed on the basis of our traditions, values, and long-term

observations of our people, we see that the mother's state of mind, her peace of mind is literally hidden as a result of her love for her child, that is, in order to bring both biological and spiritual values into the world [9].

Specialists working in many countries of Eastern and Western Europe believe that the first communication in the process of child development is communication with one person- usually with the mother - is ideal for the full development of the baby. Such communication is characterized by a fullness of affection, a wealth of games and interactive dialogues. The results of the research conducted within the framework of this problem show that physical, biological and psychological freedom in infancy and childhood are the main factors contributing to the correct formation of a child as a person. In addition, the initial communication of the infant with the mother serves as the basis for the formation and development of such a wide circle of communication as a grandmother, sister. In the early periods of a child's development, it is very necessary to take care of him around himself. At the same time, the richer these communication relationships are, the healthier and more confident the child will grow. The period preceding the child's reaching the age of one year is a period of nonverbal (unconditional) communication, when all changes in it begin to penetrate into the tiered circulation as a result of direct sensitive-emotional relationships with loved ones, especially with the mother, signs associated with language and sounds. If the care shown by the father and mother is constant and sincere, that is, a real, caring mother will try to satisfy all the needs of her child simultaneously with her heart and immediately, for example, she will do such work as breastfeeding on time. In this process, the integrity of the mother-child with the body is a specific feeling that is often caused by the experience of "holding" in science (from the English word "holding", "retention"). That is, the mother, holding the child by the hand, feels the changes in the child through her senses, which the body feels when it hits the body. The infant also feels his mother in such a close sensitive-emotional way that even at a certain distance he knows that the mother is coming, approaching and "now takes her in his hands." This is exactly what psychologists call the leading activity in a child, which gives it great importance [1].

According to foreign experts, mothers with low "holding" experience have a lot of personal problems, and they feel almost nothing, even when they hold a child in their arms. Such babies may have certain problems in the development of psychological functions, which later occur unintentionally, for example, voluntary concentration of attention on something, voluntary memorization of this or that thing, communication, logical thinking, etc. [9]

Communication, psychological functions related to speech activity are often formed in the process of synchronization. A mother who has the ability to pamper her child and know his feelings usually goes beyond his entire behavior in the development of the child's psyche, the skills of how to use them.

In order to better understand the experience of retaining the mother as a subject of caring for the child, it is necessary to resort to work on maternal readiness. S.Y. Meshcheryakova [8] and others studied maternal readiness, the hypothesis of mental readiness of the mother, the subjective-object attitude of the mother to the child, determining the behavior of the next mother. Subject-oriented communication manifests itself in the attitude of an adult to a child as a person (M.I. Lisina) [6]. S.Yu. Metsheryakova [7] and others distinguish three groups of women expecting a child. It is shown that these groups are in a different direction to the child with whom he will have a different relationship. The authors come to the conclusion that mothers of the first group prefer a subjective attitude to the child, while mothers of the second group prefer an objective one, mothers

of the third group understand the result obtained by a mixed and intermediate attitude, that is, the subject-object attitude of the mother to the child.

In our opinion, the "object" attitude to the child requires further study. If we take into account that an infant in an object relationship initially manifests itself as an object of care, socio-psychological, medical influence, then this means that the mother has a manipulative attitude towards the child, that is, these mothers should be able to perform the procedure with the child, not counting on his desires and interests. Mothers of the first group are characterized by a lack of sensitivity, tenderness and interest in the child: he talks badly to the child, does not show interest, watches the child from the side. In this case, the mother gives an idea of the value of the child and the absence of a positive emotional attitude towards him. A mother can treat her children in a positive way in different ways: she loves them, she is in a positive attitude, she uses them to her advantage [10].

The cognitive development of the child, that is, the upbringing of thoughts, the formation of a worldview, the behavior of the mother strongly influences this. According to the observations of European experts, every movement of the mother, facial expressions, treatment that the child does to himself, standing over the child, manipulation are manifested in individual phrases, words that the child gradually absorbs[2]. Based on our personal observations, it turned out that the mother's behavior is increasingly becoming silent for the child, logical and illogical actions, gestures, which later, even when the child begins to pronounce individual words, return to the mother's subconscious with facial expressions, pronunciation styles. Thus, with the direct participation and help of the mother, the child learns the world, learns, the scale of his imagination about himself is gradually increasing.

In order to understand the above scientific and linguistic experience of "holding", let's consider the relationship between individuals in typical Uzbek families. When our grandmothers watch the babies of young mothers, we can often observe that they are able to feel in advance that he is thirsty or hungry without crying. It can also be called a manifestation of a skill formed in a specific healthy family environment, which can be called part of one type of holding.

Since the middle of the XX century, psychologists have studied the initial relationship of an infant with people who take care of him, and began to use the term "kindness" in relation to this process. This concept can be explained by strong mutual closeness, two-way intense feelings and emotional ties.

We have observed in our own studies how much kindness a child shows to those who care for the child, and have benefited from the "unfamiliar situation" test, which has been used in several studies. The main purpose of the test is to evaluate the kindness of the mother-child, this test can be called a small performance. During this test, an unfamiliar room with toys will be involved, in which a mother, a one-year-old child and one stranger will take part. During the experiment, the mother leaves the room once or twice. For the first time, a mother leaves her child with a stranger for three minutes, and then she is left alone. Here analyzes the behavior of the child when he is alone and the mother's return to the room, the conclusion is made. The landscape is also diverse in two situations, both are extremely natural. Children who were very kind to their mother were always with their mother. Such children are more inquisitive, sociable, independent and shy than their 2, 3, 4 and 5-year-old peers, their level of development is moderately developed. In the course of research, it was found that 32% of children were not kind to their mother, they were divided into shy and stubborn groups. Over time, such children will have a strong sense of striving for independence. Foreign psychologists have also found that when observing three categories-loving,

shy, stubborn children, they radically differ from each other in their behavior, in the development of the psyche and in communication with peers.

Caring children show that they are ready for joint activities at the age of 18 months, their enthusiasm is high and their perseverance is high. And at the age of two, he will be able to engage in active communication with peers, play toys in order and use his imagination in various games. Five-year-olds also have such differences. And then, in primary school, children who are very kind, who are able to achieve good achievements even in school, enter into active communication with peers and adults.

The analysis of numerous studies links the socio-psychological development of a child with the compassion and insight of his mother. During the study, it was found that the mothers of children who were very kind were extremely observant and attentive to their child's questions. In addition, mothers of one-year-old very kind children are able to respond competently to their every action and adjust the feeding time and the child's play to each other. Other researchers have also noted that mothers of such children can intelligently determine the needs of their children and learn from their facial movements and voices what they need, when, what they need.

Studies again show that children who start walking, that is, children who experience physical exertion, if kindness does not manifest itself, can understand their own "I" in them and cause disturbances in the formation of their speech. If children love someone very much in the first year of life, then the unpleasant effect of an unhealthy relationship made with him at the age of two will be even less.

In the relationship of a family person, the significance of the role and embodiment of the mother again lies in the fact that before the child reaches the age of one year, the father and the mother see the personality as an object of the mother and begin to perceive the father as a separate person, starting from the age of one year [4].

Based on the above analysis as a methodological basis, we considered that the quality system of maternal experience and its characteristics carried out at different stages of child development are adequate for presenting the results of observation.

The study of the first signs of maternal retention experience the initial base is based on cases of manifestation of maternal signs, counting the ideas of pregnant women about the functions of motherhood and its relation to the child[3]. In determining these fantasies, projective methods can also serve, such as drawings "My child now", "My child in the future", as well as associative methods for determining the association with the words "child", "mother". The use of free associations and descriptions allows for a meaningful analysis of the particular meanings of the words "child", "mother" for pregnant women. The general scheme of the associative experiment is such that the stimulus phrase is given to the subject and it is required to give him the first associative that comes to mind. In a free associative experiment, examiners are not subject to restrictions on the choice of associations. Examiners work with meanings in the "order of application", which allows them to identify some incomprehensible components of meaning. Many researchers believe that the nature of the association will depend on the age, gender, information, profession of the examiner. This means that the associative technique is reflected as the cognitive structure of the linguistic meaning, the individual characteristics of the subjects, their particular meanings. In some semantic components of the meanings of this stimulus word, we proceeded from the fact that in the meaning of associations and in the description of words there are some values of attributes of the basic maternal experience. The obtained associations and descriptions were analysed from the point of view of the presence of these values in each researcher.

Quantitative data in the analysis of the association and description of the words "child", "mother", reflecting the initial base of maternal experience in the group of pregnant women we observed, are shown in Table 1.

Table-1

The number of associations to the word "child" (%)

Perception		Sympathy				Subject of training			The subject of the child's courtship		
Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Attention to the child	Empathy	An adequate response	Total score	SOP	Subjectivity	Total score	conditions that constitute the	Procedures necessary for life
42	42	42	7	37	0	5	1	4	52	40	12
27,3	27,3	28,5	4,5	24,0	0	3,2	0,6	2,6	33,7	26,0	7,7

From Table 1, which presents the results of the analysis of the word "child", it can be concluded that from the signs of the initial base of the maternal experience of retention in a pregnant woman, the sign of the quality of reception "positive emotional attitude to the child" and the sign of the quality "empathy" were more pronounced. Associations reflecting a positive attitude of a woman to a child ("beautiful", "good", "warm", "love", etc.) were identified.

As mentioned above, the initial base includes empathy towards the future child of the future mother, attention to him, an adequate reaction to his actions, his thoughts about respect for the individuality of the child, "tenderness" from the attributes of the mother's holding experience. The future child of a pregnant woman can be considered as the initial empathy of the child with various ideas about his individual characteristics: appearance, abilities, willpower, age, actions, understanding. For example, "small", "smart", "boy", "capable", "red-faced", "smiling", "crying", "skinny", "cheerful", "understanding" and so on, the empathy of the mother to the child is expressed in understanding her feelings and thoughts after childbirth. An empathic mother communicates with a child, seeing that her previous thoughts about the child do not correspond to her real characteristics, abandons her initial thoughts about him. However, the fact that a pregnant woman has an idea of the various qualities of her unborn child can serve as her initial future empathy.

At this point, it is permissible to emphasize the feature of Sympathy "attention". Many considerations are involved in the word "child" in the association, such as "attention", "care", "taking care of the child". The mother's concern for the child may arise as a result of her thoughts and actions about him, about her calmness, as well as attention to the child. A pregnant woman's concern for her future child can serve as a starting point of "attention to the child". As for the quality of the basis of the "subject of learning", it manifests itself mainly in the associations "upbringing", "responsibility", "maternal duties" as a sign of "subjectivity".

According to our data, a large group of associations with the expression of ideas about motherhood of a pregnant woman as a "subject of child care" has been identified. These are the

subjects and conditions that characterize the child's vital activity, as well as associations that make sense of the procedures necessary for his vital activity. For example, "cradle", "vitamins", "toys", "diapers", as well as "washing", "sewing" «walking», "mother", "feeding".

The data in table 2 indicate that the descriptions obtained for the word "mother" are largely consistent with the data of the association analysis. The differences are that the descriptions respect the individuality of the child's mother, considerations reflecting her attention have three meanings. For example "you need to have your own point of view" "a small person with his own character" "a person with a capital letter", "respect the child as a big person" and "requires attention". A positive emotional attitude is expressed in such arguments as "there should be joy" "childbirth", "the closest person". Empathy for the child should be "striving for knowledge" "comprehensively developed", "healthy" "cheerful", "sociable", etc.

The initial basic quality of the "subject of learning" is also largely attributed to the sign of "subjectivity" ("learning", "development and upbringing", "working with him"). The descriptions of associations reflected relatively more considerations characterizing objects, conditions and procedures, such as "shirt-making", "requires care", necessary for the child's vital activity.

Table-2

Number of descriptions for the word "child" (%)

Perception		Sympathy				Subject of training				The subject of the child's courtship			
Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Respect for individuality	Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Respect for individuality	Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Respect for individuality	Total score	Positive emotional attitude
53	47	34	6	2	32	0	4	1	0	3	22	15	7
37,0 %	32,0 %	31,5	4,7	1,6	25,2	0	3,2	0,8	0	2,4	17,3	11,8 %	5,5 %

The difference between associations and descriptions can be explained by their linguistic and informational differences: the descriptions involve reasoning expressing respect for the child, while the associations have more words reflecting the attributes of the unborn child, expressing the objects and procedures necessary for his care. A few words that do not fall under the above criteria characterize the existential state of the mother with the "future", "new feelings" and family members of the child: "father", "grandmother", "grandfather", "generation".

Table-3

The number of associations to the word "mother" (%)

Perception	Sympathy	Subject of training	The subject of the child's courtship
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Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Respect for individuality	Attention to the child	Empathy	An adequate response	Total score	SOP	SOP	Subjectivity	Total score	Subjects and conditions that constitute the provision of life	Procedures necessary for life
64	64	25	1	20	5	0	8	1	0	7	24	20	4
36,2	36,2	14,6	0,6	11,2	2,8	0	4,5	0,6	0	3,9	13,5	11,2	2,3

From the data in Table 3, it can be concluded that the word "mother" was given in relation to the word "child" in associations, and all the basic attributes of maternal experience were contained in descriptions. For example, the following associations express a positive attitude of a pregnant woman to a child: "warmth", "a woman who loves children", "kind", "pleasant", "love", "smile", "gentle". Associations reflecting the empathy of expectant mothers represent not only various characteristics of the unborn child (as in the word "child" in the association), but also a characteristic of the quality of maternal experience – "understanding", "caring". The expression "empathy" is weakly traced in the word mother in association (compared to the word child in association). In this association, the signs of the quality of the "subject of learning" are more clearly expressed – "subjectivity", the words "responsibility", "educator" are used [9].

The word "child" refers to a relatively large group of associations that reflect the imagination of the mother as a child and the family of the "subject of care", as in associations ("comfort", "sweets", "household", "kitchen", "child care", "supplier", "laundry", "cooking", "feeding"). In the word "child" in associations, the imagination of the mother as a subject of care is more expressed, and in associations with the word "mother" reflections on the relatively general qualities of the mother as a subject are reflected.

Table-4

Number of descriptions for the word "mother" (%)

Perception		Sympathy					Subject of training				The subject of the child's courtship		
Total score	Positive emotional attitude	Total score	Respect for individuality	Attention to the child	Empathy	An adequate response	Total score	SOP	SOP	Subjectivity	Total score	Subjects and conditions that constitute the provision of life	Procedures necessary for life
42	42	23	0	15	7	1	10	1	0	9	19	16	3
29,8	29,8	16,3	0	10,6	5,0	0,7	7,1	0,7	0	6,4	13,5	11,4	2,1

As the data in Table 4 show, the content of the description of the word "mother" basically coincides with the content of the same phrase. A positive emotional attitude towards a child means "loving children", "loving", "pleasant", "the closest person", etc. is characterized by descriptions. The idea of empathy is expressed by the following reasoning: "you can open your heart to him",

"you can understand everything", "you can forgive everything", "you can ask for everything". Reflections on the mother's mindfulness are manifested in such expressions as "always feeling the need for someone", "mindfulness", "taking care of your children". His quality of "adequate response" may have been reflected by the "calm" feedback. The basic quality of the maternal experience of the "subject of learning" is also expressed mainly by the sign of "subjectivity".

In the descriptions of the word "mother", as well as in the descriptions of the question "child", the words describing the objects and conditions necessary for the child's life are poorly expressed ("a good housewife", "creates conditions for the child to feel good", "child's health", "freedom and regularity"). The description and associations with the word "mother" express a large group of meanings reflecting the characteristics associated with the role of the mother as a housewife ("good housewife", "creates comfort in the house", etc.), as female characteristics: "beautiful", "modern", "intelligent", "restless" and as a family support: "economic assistance", "spiritual assistance", "role model", etc.

According to the results of data analysis, the words "child" and "mother" can be distinguished from the basic quality of the mother's initial holding experience in phrases and descriptions - reflections on the attitude of a pregnant woman to her child: "acceptance" – a positive emotional attitude to the child, "rabies" – "empathy", "attention", "respect for the child's personality".

As for the mother, fantasy as a "subject of study" is almost not expressed. In accordance with the content of our sample data, the image of the mother in pregnant women is formed as a "subject of upbringing" and "subject of child care". The impressions reflected little maternal subjectivity and reflected the woman's ability to socialize the child in various manifestations of activity and communication. For our expectant mothers, the idea that from the first days and months of a child's life it is necessary to socialize is considered significant. Several women had associations "play", "play", "initiative in children's games". This feature is reflected in the associations in the style of "positive emotional attitude", in the comments to the description of the question "respect for the individuality of the child", "mother". Also, the definition of the question "child" weakly involved words denoting the subject and circumstances necessary for the child's life ("a good housewife", "a child creates conditions for him to be well", "child's health", "freedom and regularity").

The basic quality of maternal experience, such as "empathy", is expressed in the female imagination of various attributes of the unborn child, as well as in comments, descriptions that directly reveal the content of empathy [5].

If the mother's holding experience in describing and reasoning about the word "child" is studied in associations belonging to the child of the initial basic quality, then the same signs in the so-called "maternal" associations and descriptions - "acceptance", "empathy", "attention", "subject of upbringing" are considered in representations related to the role of the mother. Thus, the mother's holding experience is that the presence of the same source base of adjectives gooseberry passes through control and finds its confirmation not in one, but in two verbal associations and descriptions. It is they who should be interconnected as a result of the commonality of the "child-mother" and "mother-child" relationships.

In addition to the basic qualitative characteristics of the maternal retaining experience, a number of expressions were identified as the subject of physical child care, representing signs of the quality of the maternal retaining in the description and associations of the words "child", "mother". They reflected the items or procedures needed to care for the child.

From the above, it can be concluded that the child feels the attachment of the mother and reacts to her in the same way. As long as the formation of personality begins with Eastern values, such as kindness, empathy, kindness in the soul of a child, there is no doubt that the foundations of the fullness of our children begin with each of us from our homes, mothers, who are the charm of our apartments. This, as the language of psychology says, a healthy family environment, begins with mutual affectionate relationships of people in them.

The results of the research work on the topic: "Family holding – the psychological mechanism of child socialization" allow us to formulate the following general conclusions:

1. as a result of studying such maternal qualities as "acceptance", "care", "subject of learning to communicate", "subject of learning to act with subjects" that affect the socialization of a child in the family, there are grounds for conclusions about the nature of the qualities of a mother who has experience and the social situation of their development.

2. Attributes of the quality of maternal holding experience are social stereotypes that have become personal aspects of the mother. As a member of the socio-psychological environment and personality, the attributes that affect the development of the child are the basis, the basis.

3. As a result of the analysis of foreign theories of child development, the experience of the maternal holding as a subject that influenced the concept of basic attributes and their properties was studied (in infancy, these are the basic attributes of the mother as a subject of learning to act with the subject). The mechanism of the influence of maternal attributes on the determination of the influence of maternal experience with signs of affectivity has been studied as a social phenomenon with cognitive and operational components. It was noted that the indicators of the social status of mothers have different effects in different periods of the child's socialization process.

4. The analysis of the development of the attributes of the parent holding experience has shown that the experience of the parent holding is divided into value-content and operational components, which depend on the ratio of its core in the attributes of the base. There is also a situational, peripheral circle of attributes, which is determined by constant situational needs and motivations, in these situations existential, superficial aspects of native attributes are considered important. They have valid components that have arisen in situations of unexpected interaction that have not been repeated before. Components can change their state and move from one group to another.

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